

Presentation a Hybrid Recommender Method to Recommend Scientific Articles using time Factors and Frequency of Search

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Abstract

Purpose: Many scholars publish scientific articles without any spatial and time limitations. Users also face hundreds of thousands of scientific-research articles and choose a sample according to their needs and interests. However, when users encounter a huge amount of information, the problem arises, and the search between them takes a lot of time. The Recommender System, influential systems for guiding the user, is among the vast volume of possible choices available to interested users, using the contextual information of articles to personalize the recommendations to them.

Design/methodology/approach: This contextual information includes the title, abstract, keywords, publisher, author and other similar items. In order to provide accurate and personalized articles to users, based on the contextual information of the title, abstract, keywords, time and frequency a user has searched for a word or downloaded an article, a proposed method using a combination Collaboration filter-based method and content-based for personalized recommendations to each user is presented. Using the Collaboration Filter Technique (user-user) to create the recommendation list, then according to articles in the recommendation list, based on the content-based technique, user articles are compared with the created list and the most relevant article is suggested to the user. Using the search time and the frequency of repetitions of the words used in the proposed method, suggests more relevant and more precise articles, in which the evaluation of the method showed that the accuracy and calling of recommendations increases when these criteria are used.

Findings: Then the proposed recommendation method compared with a few basic articles and the results show a better performance of the proposed method than the basic articles.

Keywords: article advisor system, personalization, contextual information, collaboration filtering method, content-based method, search time, the frequency of repetitions.

Introduction

Scientists usually rely on sharing their research results to gain peer, research and financial opportunities; and publications is the most popular way to share knowledge. In the past decades, academic publications have had dramatic changes since electronic format replaced with printing format. The popularity of Internet helps electronic publications to publish more research in the area. Therefore, the distribution of publications in general has become simpler and the widespread publication of the Web has increased at higher levels of publications. Researchers often share their research through the web, journal, articles, conference and presentations currently.

Mas-Bleda and colleagues identified three types of websites for distribution and publication of scientific articles: personal, institutional and social.

Personal and institutional websites are created, respectively, by scholars and academic institutions to provide academic information. Social web sites allow researchers to automatically submit articles and research results; for example: LinkedIn, Academia.edu, Research Gate, Google Scholar (Yu,2016).

Today there are many methods for scientific recommendation on such articles(Beel,2016) , which most of them are based on two content-based algorithms and Collaborative refinement, but there are two other methods, one of them is knowledge-based algorithm, and the other is combination method that can be a combination of combination of three other methods. The main idea of the content-based methods in the article recommendation systems, the user's interest and priority of study that has previously studied, is

determined by the content of scientific research., In this way, although the focus is on finding similarities between items or scientific papers, the collaborative refinement methods act as extraction and using similar user's feedback without analyzing the content and focus on similarity between users. These approaches have been introduced and evaluated in more than 170 research papers, as well as patents, lectures and blogs (Beel,2016).

Articles recommendation systems are content based and reference-based that return results by keywords. Contextual-based recommendations are usually done by using specific keywords provided to search engines such as CiteSeer and google scholar (Carageu,2013)]. In recommendations based on referrals, the purpose of the referral recommendation is to help authors in selecting the most relevant articles for referring to the potential number of resources, that the referencing relevance depends on the content of the article; For referral, the contextual next to the bracket ([[] is used, in such a way that a certain number of words are used before and after referrals, few used sources indicated by the recommendation engine in the predefined (Rokach, 1978).

In the form of referral recommendation, the concept of referrals and the content of articles (documents), in fact, there is a completely different nature, and the translation model can be a bridge between these gaps.

The interest in Web-based recommendation systems is very high because personalized services are an important factor for shopping malls and Internet service providers. Researchers and academics save their research information and others' on the

Internet and share them among each other and eventually organize them. In the research (Hong, 2012&2013), a personalized recommendation system has been introduced that increases the accuracy of research articles, and it can be a specific, Feasible and applicable domain for developing recommendation system.

Considering that in a system, users usually share different domains of articles that they have specific preferences for specific domains, in the research (Wang, 2012), it is assumed that the user's interests can be extracted from their behavior on the site, which is calculated (when they visit pages). By collecting and analyzing user's behavior, they have approached user's interests and created a personalized recommendation model that selects nominated articles for recommendation. Their experiments showed that the user-behavioral recommendation model increases the accuracy of the recommendation. If users have just registered or they are not active or even they have little behavioral information, the system can't get knowledge about their priorities. Also, for the implementation of user-centered personal recommendation, the system requires tracking user's behavior to collect information that includes user's searches, scope of work, published articles as well as friends or people associated with them in this field. Some of techniques used to personalize are "Collaborative filtering"(Sripadh, 2018), "Learning Agent filter", "Rule-Based filtering". Collaborative filtering means creating user profiles based on many similar behaviors to other users (Sripadh, 2018). The learning agent filter tracks the user's behavior by collecting user's feedback and keeping the information implicitly. This also means "learning from user's shoulder ". Rule-based filtering means creating user's profiles based

on the user's search history and filtering the data collected using some of the data mining techniques (Sripadh, 2018).

Filtering information is the process of constructing user's profiles, which is called as user's modeling. User's specifications built according to user's preferences and needs. A user's profile constructed based on a set of Explicit or implicit user's information that identifies the user's long-term and current interest and stores it in the profile. Creating user's profiles and using it in the recommendation process increases the efficiency of the recommendation system in terms of time and accuracy. Because there is more interaction with the user, accurate profiles can be created according to for a particular user. In this regard, the main purpose of this paper is to provide a recommendation system of personalized articles based on researchers' priorities and preferences at a specific time, which in the previous research all user's preferences have considered from the beginning to the searching period; If the user does not take his other basic preferences, in inappropriate recommendations will be suggested to the user. In this study, user's preferences in a timespan, as well as the frequency of searching a particular word which has not been considered in previous research are taken into account.

Ontologies are defined to link knowledge to a particular field in terms of relative concepts, the relationships between these concepts and examples of these concepts. In the field of Information retrieval (IR), when a user searches for a query, he uses traditional methods, such as word-based methods or natural language queries. A large amount of unordered information is retrieved that there are weak semantic relationships between

them and are not relevant to the user. To avoid the above problems, we use an ontology to build user profiles.

The proposed method for recommendation articles is from a collaborative and content-based hybrid combination method using the user-user collaborative filtering method create a list of similar users. In regular recommendation systems, all items that have similar users are proposed to the current user, but in the proposed system using the content-based method, articles that are most similar to the user's articles returns to the user as recommendations. In order to improve the proposed method, the frequency that a user searches keywords or words in a certain timespan will be considered so this makes it more relevant to the user's interests and old user's interests are not recommended.

The organization of this article is as follows: Section 2 reviews the relevant background in this field, Section 3 introduces the research methodology, Section 4 is the outcome and evaluation of the research method, and finally, Section 5 concludes.

2. Related works

Scientific articles recommendation system

This article (Champiri, 2015) is a targeted review of well-known background recommendation system that examines the methods of recommendation, which include classical and concontextualual methods.

Classical or 2D methods are divided into three categories: content-based categories (CB), collaborative filtering (CF) and knowledge-based (KB) and contextual methods combination of contextual information with classical recommendation

for more accurate prediction of user's preferences and interests. This concontextualual information is categorized into three main groups: user, documents, and information area.

In the research (Jokar, 2016) for each article, a profile containing background information such as title, abstract, keywords, and words that identify the scope of each article has been created. For each user, a profile which includes the user's field is formed, and finally, using the cosine similarity between articles range and the user's domain, the articles that are the most similar to the user's domain recommended to the user. In addition to the keywords used in this research, word domain detector and words that have been mentioned more than twice in the abstract are used to determine the scope of the article more precisely; To evaluate the system also 5 volunteers, whose degrees listed too, are used. According to the evaluations performed on the system, the performance of system is satisfactory.

In the past 16 years, more than 200 research papers have been published on the Research paper recommendation systems. This article (Beel, 2016) reviews these articles and provides some descriptive statistics in this paper, as well as discusses major advances and shortcomings and an overview of proposed concepts and approaches.

The authors have found that more than half of the recommendation approach uses content-based filtration (55%). The collaborative filter has been applied by only 18% of the examined methods and graphics-based recommendations by 16%. Other recommendation concepts include stereotyping, item-oriented recommendations, and hybrid

recommendations. Content-based filtering approaches mainly used articles that users had tagged, browsed, or downloaded. TF-IDF was the most used weight than in relation to other criteria. In addition to simple terms, n-grams, topics and quotes are used to model user's information needs.

Personalized recommendations

It's hard for researchers to identify favorite articles from digital libraries. This has attracted the researchers' attention to the implementation of the recommendation system (RS) in the field of academic literature. Content-based techniques and collaborative filters when applied in the field of scientific literature, reflect researcher's personal preferences in recent times, popularity, and so on.

This article (Dahnda, 2018), proposes a personalized approach based on High-Utility Itemset Mining (HUIM) for scientific literature. This method uses the content of the article with a personal preference for preparing recommendations. The authors recently used a highly efficient HUIM algorithm, introduced in the literature, to have values that are more user. The experimental evaluation assessment proves that the proposed method satisfies the researcher's individual needs, as well as the recommendation systems of the research article in a complex, time and space environment.

In the research(Hong ,2012&2013), a personalization recommendation system has been proposed that would increase the accuracy of research articles, and it can also be used to develop a specific domain recommendation system. The architecture of the proposed system consists of user interface, crawler, conversion, extractor,

filtering and finding keywords, administration profile, user profile and databases. The user interface interacts with users, which provides users with input and output topics for each crawler. The crawler writes articles from Google Scholar, saves URL of each article in one place and converts all of them into a special format. Extractor extracts article title, keywords, abstract, and the main body of each research article in the contextual form. If the article does not have keywords, the keyword title will be extracted from the title of the article. In the proposed algorithm for extracting keywords first the deterrent characters are deleted, then the keywords in title and introduction, the keywords specified for the article extracted by the author and the keywords on the first page of the article.

A user's profile is collected with a single click on a research article. Each time an article is selected, the frequency of the domain, subject, and the keywords of the profile increases, and then the rate of each occurrence and the reflection of the user's profile are recalculated. To calculate the similarity generally used the cosine similarity to solve the cold problem.

Prior studies of paper recommendation methods that consider historical user preferences rarely adequately address the complexity of user preferences and interests. This paper (Li 2021) proposes a method to recommend personalized papers based on a heterogeneous network that includes papers, venues, authors, terms, and users as well as the relations among these entities. They investigate meta-paths in the network to capture user preferences and apply random walks on these meta-paths to measure recommendation scores of candidate papers to target users. They employ a personalized

weight learning process to discover a user's personalized weights on different meta-paths using Bayesian Personalized Ranking as the objective function. A global recommendation score is calculated by combining recommendation scores on different meta-paths with personalized weights. They conducted experiments using two different datasets and the results showed that the proposed method performed better than other baseline methods.

In the paper recommendation system, authors and papers and the interaction of their information have a crucial impact on the efficiency and accuracy of the recommendations. However, most recommendation systems are usually designed based only on users. Therefore, Hao(2021) proposes a method based on the author's periodic interest and academic graph network structure to obtain as much effective information as possible to recommend papers. Extensive offline experiments on large-scale real data show that our method outperforms the representative baselines.

Research method

This research is done in two stages. In the first stage we deal with the data that contains information such as identification, activities (history of reviewing and uploading articles and projects), scope of work, background information of the articles (title, abstract, keywords). Some of these information needs to be processed to recommend.

In the second stage, Collaborative combination method (CF) and content-based approach (CB) is used to recommend. To create the recommendation list the CF technique (user-user) is used, then based on the articles in the recommendation list according to the CB technique is compared with user's articles and the most relevant article is suggested to the user. Also, at this stage, we try to improve the recommendation of the proposed method by using the criteria for the frequency a user searches for a word or downloads an article. The proposed method is presented in Figure 1, after collecting the data set in the first step, the raw data is pre-processed using the recommended techniques in the second step articles will be recommended to users.

Figure1: Overview of proposed method

Data collection

The papers used in this dataset have been collected from IEEE conferences and journals in computer, power, and mechanical domains, which were published during 2013-2015. Using a crawler that receives the URL of each article as an entry and provides background information such as article title,

abstract, keywords (including keywords used by the author for the article, terms used by the IEEE, Controlled indexes in INSPEC and uncontrolled indexes in INSPEC) extract as output in the form of XML. A sample of the data shown in Figure 2. The datasets are divided into two training subpages for training (80% of the entire dataset) datasets for the recommendation of the test set.

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<paper>
<Title>Detecting Rare Actions and Events from Surveillance Big Data with Bag of Dynamic Trajectories</Title>
<Abstract>Surveillance video is increasingly becoming the "biggest big data".
This presents an unprecedented challenge for analyzing and mining the meaningful information
(e.g., Rare actions or events) in such a huge amount of videos. Recent studies have shown that
feature-trajectories-based methods are effective to encode motion information in video,consequently
demonstrating superior performance in action and event detection. However,in existing methods, distance
between two trajectories is often measured by linear models,which may be not robust enough when the lengths
of trajectories are variable. Moreover,due to the rare distribution of target actions or events, the traditional
classifier oftentends to identify all samples as negative, consequently producing heavy performance bias. To
address both two issues, this paper proposes a trajectory descriptor, BoDT (Bag of Dynamic Trajectories),and
a multi-channel uneven SVM. By utilizing the DTW (dynamic time warping) algorithm to measure the similarity
between two trajectories, BoDT is robust for variable-length trajectory representation.Meanwhie, as an extension
of SVM with uneven margins, the proposed multi-channel uneven SVM can successfully identify rare events by
adjusting a margin parameter to make the classification boundary properly moved away from the positive training
examples. Extensive experiments on several benchmark datasets including KTH, YouTube, Olympic, MIT, QMUL and
TRECVID demonstrate that our approach is feasible and effective.</Abstract>
<DomainsAndKeywords>
Big Data;image classification;object detection;
support vector machines; video signal processing;video surveillance;BoDT;DTW;bag of dynamic trajectories;
classification boundary; dynamic time warping;event detection;multichannel uneven SVM; rare action detect
surveillance Big Data;surveillance video;trajectory descriptor;Big data; Conferences;
Multimedia communication;
</DomainsAndKeywords>
</paper>
<paper>
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Figure 2: A sample of the dataset

Stage One: Preprocessing

To use the article information, a profile is first created for each article. Then, the elimination deterrent words algorithm, which includes punctuation marks and unimportant words, and does not contain any part of the information, apply to the title and abstract of the article(Ganapathi, 2017), then, using the Porter Root Algorithm, the remaining words are rooted in which the suffixes, prefixes, and

plural marks are deleted and all the words come to their root form (Makrahchi, 2017). One of the tools used for ontology in computer science is Wordnet, which is a large lexical database of English words. This database classifies nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs into a set of synonyms that each category expressing a distinct concept. Synonyms are linked together using semantic-conceptual relationships and lexical relationships.

Then, using the famous tf/idf algorithm, as bigram, the roots are weighed (Lan, 2009) After weighing all the text sections of the articles, these weights and the identifier of each article in a useful matrix, which is in the form of a key-value, is created as the middle hadoop file; so that the key or line number is the article ID and the value or column are the words is stored, and the numbers inside the matrix is the weight of tf/idf in the article and its domain. That's the 80% part of the educational dataset.

Second step: Recommendation System

According to Figure (1), at this stage, the recommendation is done in two steps.

1. Recommendation based on CF-CB

At this stage, according to user-item approach (CF), recommendation is made to the users based on articles that they have read and those users who have such a history in reading; as described below:

First, for each user, the articles they read are identified, then among the users, the individuals who have such a history in reading the articles are identified too, after that the articles they have read are examined and the degree of similarity of articles is measured compared to the Current user's article (based on content) and n best-recommended articles that have most similarity are recommended to the user.

There are various techniques to find similarities or the distance between users or items. For example, Euclidian distance, Jaccard similarity, Pearson correlation, and cosine similarity criterion(Cosine) (Han,2011). In this research, Jaccard's similarity has been used:

$$sim^{jaccard}(i,j)=\frac{|U_i \cap U_j|}{|U_i \cup U_j|}$$

Formula 1

In this relation $|U_i \cap U_j|$, is the number of users who read both the article i and (intersection) the article j. The denominator is the union of users who have read the article i or j (minus the number of shared users).

2. Recommendation based on time and frequency of search (RTNS)

In this method, first, all users' amount of interest in searched keywords based on the time and frequency of the searching the article contains a user label is calculated, and secondly, the first recommendation algorithm is used.

• **Step 1:** The first step is to calculate the user's interest rate u to the label t :

$$I_u(t) = \sum_{ts \in Tts} \log\left(\frac{f(t,ts)}{2^{s-1}+m}\right)$$

Formula 2

In the above relation, $f(t, ts)$ represents the number of times the user ts has downloaded t tagged files at intervals ts . It should be noted that from time interval data, day and month is extracted (Due to the time limitation). S also indicates the difference between the word (s) which the article with the tag t has been searched and downloaded by the user u , $s = 1$ meaning that the tag is placed in the current word. Finally, m is defined as the difference between the month and the current time. $m = 0$ also means the article with the label t , has been downloaded this month. Using the relation 4 given more importance to recent added tags.

• **Step 2:** Calculate the similarity of labels: In this step, the similarity of labels is calculated based on two user-tag relationships (labels for articles added by users) and article-tags:

$$Sim_{u-t}^{jaccard}(t1,t2)=\frac{|Ut1\cap Ut2|}{|Ut1\cup Ut2|}$$

Formula 3

$$Sim_{f-t}^{jaccard}(t1,t2)=\frac{|Uf1\cap Uf2|}{|Uf1\cup Uf2|}$$

Formula 4

Formula 3 is the ratio of the number of users who collectively searched and downloaded articles from the labels $t1$ and $t2$, and the denominator denotes the user community (number of users who downloaded the $t1$ tag, plus the number of users who downloaded the $t2$ tag, minus intersection or the numerator). Here, all users are the same as the current user in the same set.

Formula 4 refers to the relationship between article and tag. As a result the numerator means the number of articles that are collectively containing the labels $t1$ and $t2$.

Second step: Recommendation

At this stage, similar to the first recommendation method (based on CF), the recommendation is made so that the set of users created in the previous step, the content-based recommendation operation, the degree of similarity of the articles to the downloaded articles and the current user's searched words (which are labeled) is done and returns n top recommendations.

4. Evaluation

Accuracy and readability are the practical criteria in data recovery area which determines the proportion of documents retrieved by the system to the user's needs (Han,2011). To express these two criteria, we can use the same expressions as in the clutter matrix used.

$$\text{Recall}=\text{TP}/(\text{TP}+\text{FN})$$

$$\text{Accuracy}=\text{TP}/(\text{TP}+\text{FP})$$

$$\text{F-measure}=\frac{2*\text{Recall}*\text{Accuracy}}{(\text{Recall}+\text{Accuracy})}$$

Formula 5

Table1: clutter matrix

	Relevant	Irrelevant
Recovered	False positive Fp	True positive Tp
Not Recovered	True negative Tn	False negative Fn

To investigate the effectiveness of the suggested recommendation model, the list of N above priority, which contains N articles with higher scores for each user, is calculated experimentally by comparing with several basic methods. The evaluation results are presented in Figures 1, 2 and Table 2.

Figure 1: Accuracy in different values of N (N-top)

According to the chart, the higher the number of recommendations, the lower the recommendation accuracy in both methods. Since the improved RTNS recommendation method is the CB-CF recommendation

method, accuracy of performance in this method is better than CF-CB method. Also CB-CF performance is better than CB and CF.

Figure 2: Recalling at different values of N (N-top)

Recalling of both proposed methods, like accuracy, decreases with increasing N, but the recommendation method RTNS gives

better results when N increases than other methods.

Table 2: F1 criteria for different values of N (top-N)

	F1-5	F1-10	F1-15	F1-20	F1-20
CB method	45.78%	46.09%	46.46%	46.82%	47.11%
CF method	43.49%	43.66%	43.91%	44.36%	44.61%
CF.CB method	82.98%	82.75%	82.46%	81.10%	79.53%
RTNS method	88.01%	87.63%	86.73%	86.41%	85.80%

Considering that with increasing number of recommendations, the accuracy and call rate has been reduced considerably, measuring F is also the same. Comparing two methods, the RTNS method provides better performance for different values of N.

Also, to demonstrate the performance of the proposed method, we compared the RTNS method with article method (jokar,2016).The two criteria of user's satisfaction and the accuracy used by the authors in the paper(Hong,2012&2013) for comparisons are shown in Formula 6.

$$SAT = \frac{\text{Number of Correct Research Papers}}{\text{Number of recommended research papers}}$$

$$ACC = \frac{\text{Not recommended by } unsat + \text{Recommended by } sat}{\text{The total number of stored articlesd for a given topic}}$$

Formula 6

According to the above formula, the SAT refers to the ratio of the number of correct research papers that corresponds to user's

domain, to the number of recommended research papers; and ACC refers to the ratio of the number of research articles correct and incorrect that corresponds to user's domain, to the sum of the number of research papers stored for a given topic. To measure user's satisfaction, we limit the maximum number of recommended articles to 20, but we do not create any restrictions for accuracy.

Similarly to(jokar,2016), for evaluating the system we also asked 20 undergraduate and postgraduate volunteers (each level of 10) and 5 PhD candidates in computer, power electrical, and mechanical fields to use the system for one month. Each user chose their own domain, according to that domain, the system recommended articles to them. The users for each use recorded the probability of the correctness or falseness of the scope of each article recommended by the system; then each user reported their accuracy and satisfaction after 1 month.

According to the above criteria and the average reported to each user, the results present our system performance compared to

the research as it is showed in Figures 3, 4 and 5 (jokar,2016).

Figure 3: The result of undergraduate volunteers

Figure 4: The result of postgraduate volunteers

Figure 5: The result of PhD volunteers

The degree of user's satisfaction and the precision of counseling varies from one stage to another for volunteers, because PhD candidates need detailed and relevant work-related recommendations and do not consider each recommended article; so the result of the precision and satisfaction of this group is lower than two other group but the performance is better (jokar,2016).

5. Conclusion

Today, users who is looking for scientific articles prefer to find their own resources in the least amount of time. Many studies have been done on the recommendation systems of scientific articles, and various methods have been used to make proposals in the recommendation systems. These methods are more based on three main methods: collaborative filtering, content-based, and knowledge-based. In the field of research article recommenders, semantic understanding of meaning and personalization plays an important role in

document retrieval. In this study, we presented two methods that the first one was a combination algorithm based on the method of collaboration and content. In the second method, to improve the performance of the recommendation, the criteria of the number of searches for keywords and downloading articles were used, which the evaluation of the results showed that the use of above criteria improves the accuracy, recalling and measurement of F in recommending articles compare to the basic methods. The proposed method was also compared with a basic article; volunteers in 3 undergraduate, postgraduate and PhD degrees are used to assess the accuracy and satisfaction of recommended articles, and it was found that the higher the level of education, the lower the results of accuracy and satisfaction, but it had better performance than the base method(jokar,2016).

Due to the time limitation for extracting user's search information, for future works it

is possible to increase the duration of the study from one month to several months or years.

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